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From Oppression to Resistance: A Study of Political Issues in Jean Rhys’ *Wide Sargasso Sea*

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Abstract:

The paper examines the political dimensions of Jean Rhys’s *Wide Sargasso Sea* through an analysis of power structures. It focuses on three primary sources of power: personality, property, and organisation. Drawing insights primarily from John Kenneth Galbraith’s *The Anatomy of Power*, the study explores how personality, property, and organisation, shaped by condign, compensatory, and conditioned power, respectively, generate resistance. The paper critically examines these power dynamics to demonstrate their role in shaping social and political hierarchies as portrayed in the socio-political landscape of the novel. It also investigates the systemic oppression faced by Antoinette in the context of colonial rule and her subsequent resistance to this subjugation. It further explores the intersection of gender, class, and colonialism in suppressing women’s rights. The study also traces the transition from subjugation to freedom and examines how female characters, in pursuit of liberation, resist and challenge oppressive structures like colonialism, patriarchy, and racial discrimination.

Keywords: Colonialism, Resistance, Race, Patriarchy, Power, Property.

Political issues are matters of public concern that involve debates, reforms, and decision-making about how to govern society. Defining women's political issues refers to matters that specifically affect women's rights, opportunities, and well-being, often reflecting the broader view of societal debates about gender equality and equity. The issues include discrimination, violence against women, access to education, political rights, and many more. These issues occur because of systemic inequalities and cultural norms, making them central to social debates, human rights, and political reforms. Addressing these concerns involves advocating for legal protections, equal opportunities, and societal shifts that ensure women's complete participation in all spheres of life.

According to Peter Morriss, as he argues in *Power: A Philosophical Analysis* (2002), it is necessary to analyse the notion of political power to understand women's political issues. Political power enables people to transform their abilities, through a process of collective decision-making, from doing one set of things into another set. Morris further holds that 'the practice in political science of considering issues has tended to lead to disastrous neglect of the overall pattern, which can leave an impression that movements attempting change are more powerful than they are.' (89) He refers to 'the stiletto heel principle' given by Tony Benn, to highlight how focusing on one issue at a time can help break through obstacles, but also limits how much change people can successfully achieve. To explain it, he argues that some groups have more power because they handle multiple issues simultaneously, while others focus only on one task. The idea is that those in power create barriers like bias and gatekeeping that make it harder for others to challenge the system. As a result, people fighting for change often have to spend so much effort overcoming these obstacles that they cannot focus on other important issues. The real power is about making things happen and achieving meaningful and lasting change.

In the novel *Wide Sargasso Sea*, Antoinette actively struggles against colonialism, patriarchy, and racial discrimination. She faces multiple layers of oppression, first as a Creole woman in a post-emancipation Caribbean society and then as a wife under Rochester's control. Antoinette mainly focuses on conquering the love of Rochester, which reduces her overall strength to resist against his domination. Unlike Rochester, Antoinette has no privilege of spreading her power across multiple issues. He represents the dominant colonial and patriarchal system, which allows him to exert control over her socially, financially, and emotionally. On the contrary, Antoinette has no choice but to resist Rochester's control over her. He renames her, inherits her wealth, and leaves her to degrade into madness. Although Antoinette's change did not bring any significant changes, she fought back for her freedom.

The study of Antoinette's status in a colonial, patriarchal and racial domain brings us to three types of power, i.e. compensatory, condign, and conditioned power, as suggested in *The Anatomy of Power* (1983) by John Kenneth Galbraith. He explains that people show compensatory power when people obey because they are rewarded for it, as being paid for a job. Condign power shows when people submit to avoid suffering or punishment, such as by following laws to avoid imprisonment. Conditioned power exists when people follow it because specific ideas or traditions convince or influence them. In short, power works through money, force, or ideology and shapes people's behaviour in society. He also divides power into three sources: personality, property, and organisation. Power comes from personality or leadership, property or wealth, and organisation. Organisation is associated with conditioned power; property with compensatory power, and personality with condign power.

Personality, first of all, is a source of power that naturally attracts followers who seek to benefit from its influence. Nevertheless, it is not only the personality, property, and organisation also influence the power structures. For example, a politician would think his/her charismatic power influences people, but money and ideology play an important role in

attaining this power. Sometimes, this may lead to the illusion of power, where a leader thinks that they are excellent and that their personality influences others.

In *Wide Sargasso Sea*, the Cosway family were once extremely wealthy, but as the story progresses, it becomes clear that the wealth has mostly disappeared. Her mother, Annette, struggles to maintain a life among Black people and her social status. At the same time, Antoinette navigates the tension between her family's fading glory and the colonial power structures in Jamaica. Mr Rochester, an Englishman married to Antoinette, took possession of his wife's property through English Law, leading him to believe that his greatness and strength allowed him to wield control over his wife. However, much of the power appears to come from family property and the colonial system, which encourages Rochester to exploit Antoinette.

For Antoinette, her identity shapes the power dynamics around her, including colonialism, family status, discrimination, and her marriage to Rochester. Her mental breakdown and insanity are the result of the oppressive forces around her, her mother's emotional neglect, colonial legacy, discrimination as a Creole, and Rochester's sense of power and control over her. Rochester thinks he has control over Antoinette because he is the husband, the superior sex, and the inheritor of her wealth. However, he is disillusioned to think of himself as a charismatic personality because it is involved with class, colonialism, and wealth. It says that Rochester's personality alone would not be able to control Antoinette; it is the wealth he inherited from her, being an Englishman and belonging to the White community. His desire to control Antoinette and her estate made him cruel and disconnected from reality. He believes that his character and strength gave him wealth, failing to recognise the external forces that have significantly contributed to his authority. Meanwhile, Antoinette is marginalised and disempowered despite being the rightful heir to her property. Rochester's inherited wealth and colonial supremacy are the real source of his influence.

The personality or leadership source of power has influenced both Rochester and Antoinette. The following power source is property or wealth, a dominant source in this novel. Property emphasises how wealth enables individuals or groups to influence and control others. Framing economic transactions as a mechanism of power suggests that property allows for the direct exertion of will over others through financial means. Material wealth is the driving force behind social and political relationships. Property is crucial in power relationships, particularly between Antoinette and Rochester. Antoinette, a Creole heiress of Coulibri and Granbois estates, enters into a marriage with Rochester, resulting in a legal and financial transfer of her wealth to her husband. It results in the inheritance loss, which depletes Antoinette's condition.

One of the reasons is the settlement of Antoinette's dowry to Rochester without thinking of Antoinette's security. Aunt Cora quarrelled with Antoinette's step-brother, Richard Mason, over Antoinette's dowry settlement; she said, "It is shameful. You are handing over everything the child owns to a perfect stranger. Your father would never allow it. She should be protected legally. A settlement can be arranged, and it should be arranged. That was his intention." (72) Aunt Cora knows about men and their attitude towards money. She requested Richard to settle the amount of dowry in Antoinette's favour so that she would not have to rely on her husband for money in the future. Apart from English Law, if Richard had settled the money in Antoinette's favour, she would not have faced such misfortune. She becomes disabled without money. A legal settlement would save her from her husband's misbehaviour. Richard trusted Rochester more than her sister because they were both English and not Antoinette. Richard said, "Why should I insist on a lawyer's settlement when I trust him? I would trust him with my life." It was not that he trusted Rochester with his own life. Instead, it was "trusting him with her life, not yours."

The other reason behind this is that Mr Rochester is a younger son of his father, and he did not have any share in his father's property, so he married a Creole woman, Antoinette, for

wealth and partly for financial security, which displays how property influences relationships. Rochester marrying Antoinette was just a formality, as he was not interested in the marriage ceremony or Antoinette:

It was all very brightly coloured, very strange, but it meant nothing to me. Nor did she, the girl I was to marry. When at last I met her I bowed, smiled, kissed her hand, danced with her. I played the part I was expected to play. She never had anything to do with me at all. Every movement I made was an effort of will and sometimes I wondered that no one noticed this. I would listen to my own voice and marvel at it, calm, correct but toneless, surely. But I must have given a faultless performance. If I saw an expression of doubt or curiosity it was on a black face not a white one. (Rhys 47)

It clearly shows his resentment towards marriage. He came there to earn wealth through marriage. According to English law, the wife's property goes to the husband; therefore, Rochester married a Creole girl. Also, Rochester did not have a choice because he was the youngest son of his father, and he got no money. Legally, a father's property goes to the eldest son, leaving Rochester penniless. In search of wealth, he came to the West Indies, a hot country, and caught a fever for about a month. Marriage as an institution plays a crucial role in Antoinette's future. She could not figure out the reason behind the marriage, which was that Mason had paid a handsome amount of thirty thousand pounds to Rochester as a dowry. After the wedding, Rochester gained control over Antoinette because the male-dominated society would now subjugate the Creole woman, leading her into insanity.

Also, the novel shows how property represents colonial power. Antoinette's family was once powerful and wealthy, but after the Emancipation Act, they lost their authority over enslaved people. To save their estate and wealth, Annette first marries an Englishman, Mr Mason, which leads her into madness. Lastly, Antoinette gets married to Mr Rochester, leading

to mental degradation and the loss of all her wealth to a colonial master. It shows that property is a straightforward way to control the will of others.

However, Adolf Berle's ideas in *Power without Property* (1959) argue that property provides financial power and influences belief and perception. The misuse of power often involves the misappropriation of money. For instance, bribery illustrates how wealth can corrupt power structures, revealing capital's influence over people. When Rochester inherited the wealth of Antoinette, he started mistreating her and made her live a hellish life. Property not only influences control over others but also beliefs. Before Emancipation, Cosways did not have wealth; they also possessed social prestige. Cosways were rich and, therefore, enslaved people obeyed and respected them. It gave Cosways both the compensatory and conditioned power over enslaved people. After Mr Cosway, this trait appears in Mr Rochester's character, who receives authority and credibility first despite his lack of wealth. It is because he is an Englishman representing the colonial power. Antoinette is unable to protect her wealth because she is a Creole woman in a colonial society where Englishmen hold power over both Creole and Black communities. Rochester gains complete control over Antoinette's wealth and her fate. The beliefs and perceptions favour Rochester, even though he manipulates and mistreats her. Essentially, it shows that wealth is not just about money but also shapes how people are perceived and how they exercise power.

The source of power is 'organisation' power, which is associated with conditioned power, or an instrument of enforcement highly subjective in character. In the novel, conditioned power plays a significant role in how Rochester controls Antoinette. At first, Antoinette has wealth and property, but being a Creole woman in a colonial society, she lacks the societal recognition that would give her true power. Rochester, on the other hand, gains dominance through legal ownership and manipulating her beliefs about herself. He isolates her and changes her name to 'Bertha,' leading her to believe she is destined to fall into madness

like her mother and making her doubt her reality and identity. It reflects Galbraith's idea that conditioned power works when individuals submit without realising it, believing their submission is natural.

Furthermore, the colonial setting also represents how conditioned power operates on a larger scale. At the very beginning of the novel, Antoinette says, "They say when trouble comes close ranks, and so the white people did. However, we were not in their ranks." (1) She sees the situation as a quasi-military one; as Creoles, she and her family feel themselves to be excluded by white European incomers and by the more respectable plantation owners. The entire Jamaica was ruled by Europeans and then by Creoles or hybrid ones. Creoles were also white, but they were not English. They have felt the difference, and so have the black people there. Politically, Europeans have greater power than any other culture. Britishers explored Jamaica, but never legally approved of Creole culture. Christophine told Antoinette, "The Jamaican ladies had never approved of my mother... because she pretty like pretty self." (1) Her mother was made to believe she belonged nowhere, creating a sense of danger.

The formerly enslaved people in Jamaica, though legally free after Emancipation, still exist in a system that keeps them economically and socially dependent on white landowners. Generations accept British rule as legitimate because conditioned power has led them to see it as a natural order. Similarly, Rochester represents England's authority over the Caribbean, and Antoinette, despite her initial resistance, ultimately falls under his control. It clearly states Galbraith's argument that organisations and systems of power often create the illusion of authority without necessarily needing to exert force. In the end, Antoinette's tragic fate shows how conditioned power can shape individuals' reality, leading them to accept their oppression and submission as inevitable.

However, oppression and suppression underline that power is never absolute, as it always leads to resistance. If power could expand unchecked, society would be dominated exclusively by those most skilled in wielding it. As a result, modern society remains in a state of balance to those subjected to power push back, creating a balance between control and resistance. This concept reflects Antoinette's struggle against Rochester's control. Antoinette first protests against Rochester's control. When he began mistreating her, she tried to rekindle his affection using obeah (folk magic) as she gave the potion made by Christophine in the hope of regaining power over their marriage. However, this attempt fails when Rochester finds out about it and takes revenge by consummating with the servant Amelie in Antoinette's presence, which drives her insane. He also wrested her identity by changing her name to "Bertha" and treating her like a puppet.

Rochester starts calling her Bertha, "Do not laugh like that, Bertha" (86) because he is fond of that name. Antoinette had an idea that Rochester was planning to snatch her Creole identity, and for that, he would first change her name. Antoinette rejects his action of changing her name, "Bertha is not my name. You are trying to make me into someone else, calling me by another name. I know that is obeah too." (94) Rochester usurps not only her money but also her identity. He hates the idea of being called Creole's husband. He hates her wife so much that her name also frightens him. Moreover, changing one's name is also related to black magic. He is trying to control her like a puppet, a doll.

Rochester sees an instance of resistance in Antoinette's actions: "I thought, and saw that tree strike its root deeper, making ready to fight the wind." (106) Now, Rochester would take Antoinette with him forever, but the 'fight' signifies Antoinette's resistance to his decision. She does not want to leave her place, but he says, "If and when it comes they will all go." It means all her efforts go in vain because he is not paying any heed to them. The soul of Antoinette is 'crying for mercy,' but he is 'not caring for these abject things.' He only thinks

of 'revenge and hurricanes.' 'Hurricanes' shows the rage inside his heart towards Antoinette and the people there.

The novel overviews Grace Poole, the woman who looks after Antoinette in England, who sees the resistance in Antoinette's eyes that she wants to go from this damned place and be free, "I will say one thing for her, she hasn't lost her spirits. She is still fierce. I don't turn my back on her when her eyes have that look. I know it." (116) Antoinette is still fiery like fire and can burn the whole world. She dares to make herself free from imprisonment. She doubted the actual name of Grace Poole but also questioned her identity, as Rochester never calls Poole by her real name. Antoinette imagines herself free from that locked attic in a beautiful dress, and she misses her looking glass, "Names matter, like when he would not call me Antoinette, and I saw Antoinette drifting out of the window with her scents, her pretty clothes and her looking-glass." (117)

Antoinette misses her old self in Jamaica when she loved herself. She had long hair, big eyes, and thick lips, and she was so fond of herself that she even tried to kiss herself in the mirror, but the mirror always came between her. The 'looking-glass' has become the bridge between her body and the soul. She tries to love herself, but cannot. It creates a chasm between her husband, who hates her and does not want to look at her. The looking glass symbolises the identity crisis. She misses the inner girl, and now, she is left with thin skin and bones. Rochester has snatched her freedom by bringing her to England and imprisoning her in the attic until she dies. Antoinette's final act of rebellion, putting Thornfield Hall on fire, symbolises her refusal to let society erase her and many non-white women from history and memory.

Christophine actively shows a resistance, which symbolises Caribbean independence and challenges Rochester's colonial authority. She openly criticises Rochester and accuses him of Antoinette's insanity and her miserable condition. Unlike Antoinette, she does not submit to

European power structures, refusing to be intimidated by Rochester's status as an Englishman. Rochester threatened her with law and order, but Christophine reiterated that no one could imprison her because she was a member of the post-Emancipation society. After Emancipation, she became a free woman living on her own, and the previous police records were also of no use. She appears to be a strong character in the novel after Aunt Cora. Rochester admits that 'she was a fighter.' They empowered themselves despite hardships. They embody the strength and courage that Antoinette and her mother need.

Hence, the paper analysed how individuals exercise power through property, conditioned beliefs, personality, and social structures, and how these three sources of power helped in achieving freedom through resistance. Rochester's act of controlling Antoinette's wealth reinforces legal and social power; however, Antoinette's attempt to resist Rochester's atrocities and the rebellious act of setting Thornfield Hall on fire shows her struggle of resistance towards the colonial and patriarchal system. Also, the systemic inequalities constrain Black people's efforts, and they remain marginalised in colonial society as Christophine retaliates to Rochester's accusations, but others fear the colonial master's supremacy over them. Finally, the paper concludes that power always generates resistance, and it remains an essential part of the struggle against oppression.

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